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D3.2 Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) Handbook

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Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package
PB	Plenary Board or General Assembly
RAI	Research Analysis Identifier
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
ML	Machine Learning
API	Application Programming Interface
SDK	Software Development Kit
RAI	Research Analysis Identifier
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
RCN	RAI Certified Node
RCH	RAI Central Hub
ML	Machine Learning
SSO	Single-Sign On
GRNET	Greek Research and Technology Network
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable

Executive summary

This deliverable aims to present the purpose of the Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) Handbook. The Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) Handbook is a website including all the specifications needed for the use of RAI in publications. Although this deliverable (Type: OTHER) provides the current information on the RAI PID, the website will be a reference point and updated during and after the completion of the development of RAISE to encapsulate the latest changes of RAI PID. The RAI PID Handbook was developed as part of the RAISE service architecture and its relating work packages, and functions as a guide for the development and utilization of the RAI PID.

1 Research Analysis Identifier Handbook Overview

The Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) Handbook is a website including all the specifications needed for the use of RAI in publications. This information relates to the architecture of the RAI Persistent Identifier, its functionality and relating technical topics. Although this deliverable provides the current information on the RAI PID, the website will be a reference point and updated during and after the completion of the development of RAISE to encapsulate the latest changes of RAI PID. The RAI PID Handbook was developed as part of the RAISE service architecture and its relating work packages, and functions as a guide for the development and utilization of the RAI PID.

2 Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) Handbook Contents

2.1 Landing page

The landing page of the Research Analysis Identifier (RAI) Handbook can be found at:

<https://pid.raise-science.eu>

Figure 1 Landing Page of RAI PID Handbook

2.2 Handbook sections

2.2.1 About

The About section describes the purpose of the RAI PID.

Figure 2 The About Page of RAI PID Handbook

2.2.2 Description

The sections in Description explain in detail how the RAI PID is structured.

2.2.2.1 Format information

This section described the format of the RAI PID.

Figure 3 The Format section of the RAI PID Handbook

2.2.2.2 Core information

The information relating to the Core records of the RAI PID is described in this page.

Figure 4 The first section of the Core information of the RAI PID Handbook

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Figure 5 The second section of the Core information of the RAI PID Handbook

Figure 6 The third section of the Core information of the RAI PID Handbook

Figure 7 The fourth section of the Core information of the RAI PID Handbook

2.2.2.3 Extended information

The extended information of the RAI PID holds the metadata of the PID.

Figure 8 The first section of the Extended Information of the RAI PID Handbook

Figure 9 The second section of the Extended Information of the RAI PID Handbook

Figure 10 The third section of the Extended Information of the RAI PID Handbook

2.3 Future revisions

Future revisions of the Handbook will follow the development of RAI PID, including updated information that is considered essential for the use and maintenance of the RAI PID by the scientific community.

3 Conclusion

This deliverable provides a summary of key information that aids in understanding the RAI PID Handbook. AUTH and VICOM partners from the RAISE consortium participated in the OA1 (Opportunity Area) Permanent Identifiers (PIDs) of EOSC during the EOSC Winter School in Thessaloniki and will participate in the sub-committee of it. The EOSC PID Policy was presented and discussed and RAISE is working on implementing it in RAI PID. Any further development will be updated on the RAI Handbook website.